

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Ismaylova B

EXPRESSION OF EDUCATIONAL IDEAS IN KARAKALPAK TOLGAWS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
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MENTION

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